

The Figurehead Beam and Forecastle of *Griffin* (1495)

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Abstract

Late medieval forecastles are prominent in iconography but remain poorly understood in archaeological terms because their supporting structures are seldom preserved. This paper reassesses forecastle timbers from the royal warship *Griffin* (*Gribshunden*, 1495) and identifies an additional timber belonging to the carved figurehead beam raised in 2015. Combined with the previously recovered section, the element can be reconstructed as a longitudinal member more than 9.5 m long. In conjunction with neighbouring timbers, this beam serves as a key diagnostic indicator for reconstructing the vessel's forecastle. The evidence permits a preliminary evidence-based estimate of the size, layout, and construction of the *Griffin* forecastle, indicating a substantial elevated platform designed for naval warfare practices. The study thus highlights the value of continued research on the superstructure of the warship and provides a new comparative framework for understanding forecastles on other late medieval and early modern wrecks.

Keywords: *Griffin; Gribshunden; carrack; medieval; early modern; Baltic; forecastle; figurehead*

Introduction

Projecting forecastles are among the most visually distinctive features of late medieval warships, yet their construction remains poorly understood. Although iconographic sources depict complex and elevated bow structures, the underlying structural arrangements are rarely preserved archaeologically. In particular, the relationship between figureheads, the stempost, and the supporting framework of the forecastle has remained largely hypothetical.

The wreck of *Griffin* (1495), also known as *Gribshunden*, offers a rare opportunity to address these questions. As one of the best-preserved late medieval royal warships, the site has produced a wide range of material relating not only to hull construction but also to elements of the upperworks (Rönby 2015; Adams & Rönby 2022; Warming & Rönby 2024). Although the wreck is partially disarticulated, numerous structural timbers are preserved either in situ or as displaced components on the seabed, indicating that parts of the superstructure survived the wrecking process.

Among these, the sculptured figurehead beam, recovered as a protective measure in 2015 by Södertörn University in collaboration with Marin Mätteknik (MMT) and Blekinge Museum, stands out as a uniquely informative element. The present author participated in both the discovery and recovery, and the timber has since remained central to research on the vessel's bow construction (Warming 2015). While the carving itself has attracted considerable media and scholarly attention (Eriksson 2015, 2020), the structural implications of the beam have only recently begun to be understood more fully in relation to the forecastle. New analysis of field documentation (Warming & Rönby 2024), which was conducted in 2023 by Södertörn University and Stockholm University in connection with the author's ongoing doctoral research, has now revealed that this element formed part of a much longer timber, significantly extending its known length and clarifying its role within the bow construction. This new finding allows for the first time an approximation of the forecastle structure.

The figurehead beam and its extension

The preserved figurehead beam consists of a carved forward section measuring approximately 3.45 m in length (fig.1). The sculpture depicts a stylised animal head with an open jaw, within which a human figure appears to be emerging or consumed (Eriksson 2015; Rönby 2021; Adams & Rönby 2022).

Fig. 1. The figurehead beam raised in 2015 by Södertörn Högskola in collaboration with Marin Mätteknik och Blekinge Museum. The beam is equipped with (A) recesses to accommodate crossbeams and (B) a recess for a vertical standing timber. The beam is broken off at the aftmost end at the point of an aperture that originally enclosed around the stempost. (Illustration: After Eriksson 2015; Photo: Ingemar Lundgren).

Beyond its decorative qualities, the beam exhibits several features indicating a structural function (Eriksson 2020). Along its upper surface, a series of rectangular rebates are arranged at regular intervals of c. 40-41 cm. These are associated with nail holes and are best interpreted as seating positions for transverse timbers, i.e. cross beams. Closer to the sculptured end, a deeper recessed rectangular area forms a distinct step, which may have served as a footing for a vertical support for a secondary level. Alternatively, a standing sculpture, as seen on the Mataró ship model, may have been positioned here (Eriksson 2015: 25f.).

At the opposite end, the beam terminates in a large, widening opening (now broken). This feature corresponds closely to the dimensions of the upper stempost and is most plausibly interpreted as a fixing point through which the beam engaged directly with this element. In front of this the underside of the figurehead beam also preserves an elongated recess, suggesting that it was supported from below, possibly by a knee or similar structural component.

Figure 2. The newly identified continuation of the figurehead beam, displaying the same sets of rebates for crossbeams and the expanding aperture (now broken) which would have accommodated the stempost (in the background). Photo: Dr. Florian Huber/*Griffin* 2023.

Recent reassessment of documentation from the 2023 fieldwork (Warming & Rönby 2024) has led to the identification of a second timber as a continuation of this beam (fig. 2). This section, measuring c. 6.31 m in length, lies in close proximity to the stempost and exhibits the same sequence of cuttings and constructional features (fig. 3). The consistency in dimensions, spacing, and overall form strongly supports their interpretation as parts of a single, originally continuous beam.

Taken together, these elements indicate a minimum total length exceeding 9.5 m. This makes the figurehead beam one of the longest known longitudinal timbers associated with the forecastle of a vessel of this period and suggests a far more extensive structural role than previously recognised.

Fig. 3. Site plan with (1) original position of the figurehead beam raised in 2015, (2) stempost, (3) extended figurehead beam, (4) tentatively identified foremast step, (5) forecastle railing elements, (6) partition beam. Illustration: Jon Adams (adopted from Adams & Rönnby 2022: fig. 6).

Implications for the forecastle

The identification of the extended beam provides a new basis for interpreting the forecastle. Rather than being supported by a series of shorter elements, the forward superstructure appears to have been organised around a single longitudinal member running along the centreline. The regularly spaced rebates along the beam indicate that crosswise timbers were seated along its length, forming the primary framework for the deck. In this sense, the figurehead beam formed the backbone of the forecastle construction.

On this basis, the forecastle can be reconstructed as an elongated structure extending well aft from the bow. The preserved features suggest a deck length of at least c. 8.6 m, measured to a point just behind the forward step. At the same time, the overhanging portion of the forecastle projecting beyond the stempost appears to have been relatively limited (only c. 2.1 m), with the sculptured section extending further forward than the deck itself.

A large transverse timber located aft of the beam, measuring approximately 6.7 m in width, likely represents a structural division marking the rear boundary of the forecastle (fig. 3; Warming & Rönnby 2024: 24-25). Although this identification remains tentative, it provides a useful indication of the potential breadth of the structure at this point. If correctly identified,

this timber provides a tentative basis for cautiously approaching the shape and extent of the forecastle, reflecting a structure that broadened towards the aft and narrowed towards the bow. Additional evidence supports this interpretation. Several railing elements have been identified in the bow area, including two fragments that together measure at least 7 m in length (with the distal end remaining obscured on the seabed). While these do not represent a complete side, they are consistent with the dimensions implied by the reconstructed plan and suggest that the forecastle was enclosed by substantial railings.

Fig. 4. Schematic reconstruction of the Griffin forecastle, illustrating the inferred relationships between the principal structural elements and the approximate dimensions indicated by the archaeological evidence. The drawing is not to scale and is based on observed spatial relationships in the archaeological material, combined with measurements derived from the central beam and the possible partition timber. The apertures for the bowsprit and foremast are shown schematically, as their precise placement and dimensions remain uncertain. Illustration by the author.

A schematic representation of this reconstruction is provided in Figure 4. The illustration is not drawn to scale but is intended primarily to visualise the inferred relationships between the principal structural elements and the approximate dimensions indicated by the archaeological evidence. It is based on the spatial relationships observed in the material, combined with

measurements derived from the central beam and the possible partition timber. The apertures for the bowsprit and foremast are likewise shown schematically, as their precise placement and dimensions remain uncertain.

Structural considerations

The extended figurehead beam has important implications for understanding how the forecastle was supported. Its length and central position indicate that it functioned as a primary load-bearing element, distributing forces along the axis of the ship rather than concentrating them at the bow. This suggests a more integrated structural solution than previously assumed in carrack shipbuilding (see e.g. Marsden 2009 84–86, 378).

The beam's engagement with the stempost is particularly significant. Rather than resting against it, the beam appears to have been fitted around the stempost through a widened opening, creating a secure connection between the longitudinal and vertical elements. This structure was further supported by a series of vertical reinforcement timbers, including external standards with rebates to accommodate the overlapping paneling of the superstructure, which have also been identified on the wreck side (Warming & Rönby 2024: 19ff., 83ff.). This would have allowed loads from the forecastle to be transferred efficiently into the hull structure.

The presence of such a substantial central beam also has implications for the arrangement of other components. In particular, it is unlikely that the bowsprit and foremast could have been aligned with the centreline without interfering with the beam. This suggests that the bowsprit and its associated opening were positioned off-centre, providing a rare glimpse into how structural constraints influenced the layout of the bow.

Overall, the combination of longitudinal and transverse elements indicates that the forecastle was a carefully engineered structure which sought to effectively integrate the hull with the superstructure. Its construction reflects a deliberate effort to balance the need for an elevated platform with the structural demands imposed by its projection beyond the hull.

Function and use

The forecastle was a substantial architectural feature. Its construction and dimensions indicate a robust working platform at the bow, which can be estimated to have covered approximately 29 m² based on the reconstructed length and width. In practice, however, the effective usable area would have been somewhat reduced by the presence of various other elements, including the bowsprit and foremast that protruded through the deck, as well as vertical supports and

railings. These calculations relate only to the reconstructed lower, or first, forecastle deck. In all likelihood, the structure was also surmounted by a second forecastle deck, as indicated by iconographic parallels and the architectural logic of the vessel.

Even allowing for these constraints, the lower platform would have been capable of accommodating a sizeable combat unit. Under conditions permitting some degree of movement, it could likely have supported on the order of a dozen combatants. In more crowded situations - such as those associated with imminent boarding actions - the number may have been considerably higher, potentially approaching twenty individuals, although this would have restricted mobility and the effective use of hand-held weapons. The total fighting capacity of the forecastle would therefore have been greater than these figures imply, since additional men could have occupied the upper deck and others may have moved into the structure from the deck below through the great arch.

The forecastle should therefore be understood as a dedicated fighting space associated with shipborne soldiers. Its elevated position would have provided clear advantages for missile deployment and close-quarters engagement. At the same time, the surrounding railings were not merely protective barriers but likely served as mounting points for light artillery, such as swivel guns, further enhancing the offensive capabilities of the bow.

Fig. 5. Ammunition-making tool chest (*Zeuglade* in German terminology) with associated contents. The solid line marks the preserved elongated side of the chest; dotted lines indicate

the estimated position of the remaining sides. Contents: (1) lead plates; (2–3) moulds; (4) the elongated side of the chest with associated iron corrosion (possibly from the lock and fittings); (5) cylindrical ‘cans’ (possibly powder containers); and (6) mould. Photo by Dr Florian Huber; outlines and annotations by Rolf Warming (from Warming & Rönby 2024: fig. 14).

Evidence from the surrounding area reinforces this interpretation. In particular, a feature located in proximity to the forecastle has previously been identified as an ammunition-production or weapon chest, i.e. a so-called ‘zeuglade’ in German terminology (Rönby 2021: 35). This feature and its contents - including multiple mould halves, lead plates, and associated materials - have previously been identified and discussed in detail (fig. 5; Warming & Rönby 2024: 30–35), forming also part of the author’s ongoing doctoral research.¹ Further analyses of this feature are planned, particularly with regard to its spatial and functional relationship to the forecastle.

In this respect, the reconstruction of the forecastle provides an essential framework for understanding the material recovered from this part of the vessel. As discussed elsewhere (Warming & Rönby 2024: 30-35), the extent and construction of the platform offer critical contextual data for interpreting artefacts such as the ammunition-production chest, as well as other associated finds and structural timbers in the bow area. Rather than representing isolated or ambiguous elements, these materials can thus be understood in relation to a defined and purpose-built working and fighting space.

Within this framework, the figurehead beam formed a key structural component. By providing a stable longitudinal support for the deck, it allowed the forecastle to operate as a robust platform capable of sustaining both personnel and weaponry, including artillery.

Discussion

The recognition of the extended figurehead beam represents a significant shift in how the bow of *Griffin* is understood. Rather than a relatively compact arrangement centred on a short decorative element, the evidence now points to a large and structurally integrated forecastle organised around a central longitudinal beam which, together with associated structural

¹ In subsequent work, Foley, Smith and Hansson (2025: 15–16, fig. 22) cite this interpretation but characterise it as ‘speculative’, deferring further interpretation pending recovery of the feature. At the same time, elements of the same chest are discussed independently by the same authors, including the identification of a mould, without engagement with the previously documented range of artefacts or the broader interpretation of the feature. The documentation from 2023, however, provides a substantially clearer basis for interpretation, drawing on high-resolution photography, photogrammetry, direct measurement, and relevant historical sources which permitted detailed analyses to be made (Warming & Rönby 2024: 30-35).

elements, provides a coherent basis for reconstructing its framework. The use of a long central beam suggests a deliberate strategy for managing structural loads, demonstrating a form of structural integration in bow construction of carracks that has not previously been documented archaeologically.

As discussed, these findings also provide important insights into specific details of Late Medieval naval warfare. The reconstructed forecastle emerges as a robust purpose-built fighting platform, designed to accommodate personnel and weaponry in a tactically advantageous position at the bow. Its size and configuration suggest that it could support a concentrated group of combatants, while also providing mounting positions for light artillery along the railings. The integration of such a platform into the ship's structural framework indicates that close-quarters combat, missile deployment, and boarding actions were anticipated and actively facilitated in the ship design. In this respect, the forecastle should be understood as a highly functional and integral component of late medieval warship architecture, rather than a secondary or purely ornamental addition.

More broadly, these results have implications beyond the *Griffin* material itself. The identification of a long central beam as a key structural element provides a new basis for recognising and interpreting analogous features on other wrecks. This is particularly significant in cases where the bow and forecastle are poorly preserved or have not been recovered. The *Mary Rose* (1545), for example, represents one of the best-preserved early modern warships, yet its forward superstructure remains largely unknown, as the bow and forecastle were not raised, apart from the stempost (Marsden 2009: 84–86, 378). In this context, the configuration identified on *Griffin* offers a plausible structural model for understanding how such projecting bow platforms may have been supported. At the same time, similar elements may now be recognised on other sites, including the *Kraveln* wreck (1525), where a comparably long central timber - potentially associated with a sculptured distal end - has been tentatively identified but requires further investigation (Warming In press). Additional fieldwork to examine this feature in greater detail is currently being planned.

At the same time, the reconstruction presented here remains provisional in certain respects. The transverse partition timber, for example, requires further analysis, and additional work is needed to clarify the precise arrangement of the superstructure and its supporting elements. Particular attention should be directed towards the newly identified continuation of the central figurehead beam on the seabed, which warrants detailed documentation for additional details and its relationship to the surrounding timbers in the bow. As this timber appears to form part of the

same structural element as the figurehead beam recovered in 2015, it also raises important considerations for heritage management and should be evaluated in terms of potential protective recovery. Despite these outstanding questions, the available evidence provides a coherent and well-founded framework for interpreting the preserved material.

Conclusion

The reassessment of the *Griffin* material has revealed that the figurehead beam formed part of a much longer structure than previously recognised, extending to over 9.5 m in length. This beam can be understood as a central supporting element within the forecastle, around which the deck was constructed, and as a diagnostic structural feature for identifying and reconstructing the extent and organisation of the bow superstructure.

By integrating the information derived from this beam with other datasets, it becomes possible to propose a first archaeological interpretation of the extent of the forecastle as a substantial elevated fighting platform. The findings demonstrate that forecastles were structurally integrated components of late medieval warships and provide new insight into their construction and function, including the possibility of approximating their capacity for combatants and armaments through the reconstructed deck area.

Further investigation will be necessary to refine this interpretation, but the results presented here establish a foundation for future work and highlight the interpretive potential of reassessing existing material in light of new observations.

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